

Development and Validation of the Sleep-Wake Disorders Questionnaire for Children and Adolescents

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Resumen

■ INTRODUCCIÓN

Los trastornos del sueño y vigilia (TSV) impactan significativamente el desarrollo y la vida diaria de niños y adolescentes, destacando la necesidad de herramientas de detección culturalmente apropiadas en México. Este estudio tuvo como objetivo desarrollar y validar un instrumento de detección para TSV en poblaciones jóvenes. Objetivo: Desarrollar y validar el Cuestionario de Trastornos del Sueño y Vigilia (CTSv) en población pediátrica.

Materiales y Método: Se diseñó el CTSv de 43 ítems elaborado por expertos, compuesto por la Sección A (33 preguntas diagnósticas) y la Sección B (10 preguntas sobre hábitos de sueño). Se llevó a cabo un estudio transversal para evaluar la validez del constructo mediante análisis factorial y la consistencia interna a través del coeficiente α de Cronbach.

Resultados: El estudio incluyó a 103 participantes de entre seis y 17 años, reclutados en dos hospitales psiquiátricos de la Ciudad de México. El CTSv demostró una fiabilidad moderada. El análisis factorial identificó dos factores principales: disomnias y parasomnias, los cuales explicaron aproximadamente un tercio de la varianza total. La consistencia interna fue $\alpha = 0.68$ para el factor de parasomnias y $\alpha = 0.25$ para el factor de disomnias. La sección de hábitos de sueño mostró que el 50% de los participantes compartían habitación, y se observó un consumo frecuente de cafeína y siestas diurnas.

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Conclusiones: El CTSV se alinea con las observaciones clínicas sobre trastornos del sueño pediátricos y proporciona información valiosa sobre los hábitos de sueño en niños y adolescentes mexicanos. Esta herramienta presenta un enfoque culturalmente relevante con potencial para la evaluación y manejo clínico de los TSV pediátricos.

Palabras Clave: *Trastornos del Sueño y Vigilia; Trastornos del Sueño Pediátricos; Investigación de Validación Psicométrica; Niños y Adolescentes.*

■ ABSTRACT

Background: Sleep-wake disorders (SWDs) significantly impact the development and daily life of children and adolescents, highlighting the need for culturally appropriate screening tools in Mexico. This study aimed to develop and validate a screening instrument for SWDs in young populations.

Objective: To develop and validate the Sleep-Wake Disorders Questionnaire (SWDQ) in pediatric populations with SWDs.

Materials and Methods: The SWDQ, a 43-item questionnaire designed by experts, comprises Section A (33 diagnostic questions) and Section B (10 questions on sleep habits). A cross-sectional study was conducted to evaluate construct validity through factor analysis and internal consistency using Cronbach's α coefficient.

Results: The study included 103 participants aged six to 17 years, recruited from two psychiatric hospitals in Mexico City. The SWDQ demonstrated moderate reliability. Factor analysis identified two main factors: dyssomnias and parasomnias, which together explained approximately one-third

of the total variance. Internal consistency was $\alpha = 0.68$ for the parasomnia factor and $\alpha = 0.25$ for the dyssomnia factor. The sleep habits section revealed that 50% of participants shared a bedroom, with frequent caffeine consumption and daytime napping observed.

Conclusions: The SWDQ aligns with clinical observations of pediatric sleep disorders and provides valuable information on sleep habits among Mexican children and adolescents. This tool offers a culturally relevant approach with potential for clinical evaluation and management of pediatric SWDs.

Keywords: *Sleep-Wake Disorders; Pediatric Sleep Disorders, Psychometric Validation Research, Children and Adolescents.*

■ BACKGROUND

Sleep-Wake Disorders (SWDs)

SWDs include a variety of conditions that disrupt the normal sleep-wake cycle, leading to difficulties in initiating or maintaining sleep, excessive daytime sleepiness, or abnormal behaviors during sleep (Zammit et al., 1999). These disorders are categorized into two primary groups: dyssomnias and parasomnias. Dyssomnias encompass conditions such as insomnia disorder (ID), hypersomnia disorder (HD), and circadian rhythm sleep-wake disorder (CRSWD), which primarily affect the quality, quantity, and timing of sleep. Parasomnias include abnormal behaviors or physiological events during sleep or transitions between sleep and wakefulness, such as non-REM sleep-activation disorder (NREMSAD), which includes sleepwalking and night terrors, restless legs syndrome

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(RLs), and nightmare disorder (ND) (AMERICAN PSYCHIATRIC ASSOCIATION [APA], 2000; APA, 2013).

Global Epidemiology in Children and Adolescents

SWDs are prevalent among children and adolescents, significantly affecting their development and daily functioning. Studies report that 20% to 30% of children experience sleep disturbances during development (Owens, Spirito, & McGuinn, 2000). These issues often persist into adolescence, exacerbated by biological, psychological, and social factors. For example, ID and CRSWD are commonly observed in teenagers, frequently worsened by academic pressures and social activities (Dahl & Lewin, 2002).

Prevalence rates of SWDs vary across studies and populations. Paiva (2017) reported ID frequencies ranging from 4% to 27%, while HD was observed in 10% to 20% of prepubertal children and 16% to 47% of adolescents (Owens et al., 2020). For NREMSAD, the prevalence of sleep terrors in children aged 3 to 10 years was 14.7%, and sleepwalking was observed in 9.2%. ND affected up to 25% of children aged 2 to 5 years and 41% aged 6 to 10 years. RL prevalence in clinical samples ranged from 1.3% to 5.9% (Paiva, 2017).

In Latin America, the prevalence of SWDs in children and adolescents reflects global trends, although regional studies are less abundant. Socio-cultural and environmental factors play a significant role in shaping sleep behaviors and disorders. For instance, a Colombian study reported insomnia prevalence at 14.9%, night terrors at 6.1%, sleepwalking at 7.4%, and nightmares at 12.8% among school-aged children (Contreras et al., 2005). Similarly, a Brazilian study noted high rates of SWD

symptoms in youth, closely linked to low socioeconomic status (Pires, Benedito-Silva, & Mello, 2007). In Mexico, while research is still developing, urban areas have shown significant rates of sleep disturbances, influenced by factors such as screen time and irregular sleep schedules (Del-Río-Álvarez, Díaz-Méndez, & Ramírez, 2013).

Screening Instruments and Psychometric Tools

Globally, several psychometric tools have been developed to assess SWDs in pediatric populations. The Sleep Disturbance Scale for Children (SDSC) is a 27-item Likert scale that evaluates the frequency of sleep disturbances, demonstrating good internal consistency ($\alpha = 0.79$) and identifying disorders such as dyssomnias and parasomnias (Bruni et al., 1996). The Pediatric Sleep Questionnaire (PSQ) is a 90-item parent-reported instrument assessing sleep-disordered breathing, snoring, and other sleep problems in children aged 2 to 18 years. It has strong reliability and validity, with significant correlations to polysomnographic findings (Chervin et al., 2000). Another tool, the Sleep Disorders Questionnaire (SDQ), includes four clinical scales for sleep apnea, narcolepsy, psychiatric disorders, and periodic limb movement disorder, with adequate internal consistency and diagnostic accuracy for pediatric use (Douglass et al., 1994).

Each of these tools, however, presents limitations. For example, the SDSC focuses on specific symptoms, potentially omitting other SWDs. The PSQ's length can burden respondents, affecting completion rates, while the SDQ requires additional validation across diverse pediatric populations.

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■ JUSTIFICATION

Given the high prevalence and significant impact of SWDs among children and adolescents, there is a need for reliable and valid screening tools tailored to Mexican populations. The development of the Sleep-Wake Disorders Questionnaire for Children and Adolescents (SWDQ) aims to address this gap by providing a culturally relevant, comprehensive, and easy-to-administer instrument. This tool assesses both SWDs and sleep habits, considering their associations with the onset or persistence of sleep disorders, providing a vital resource for clinicians and researchers in Mexico (Kansagra et al., 2020).

■ OBJECTIVE

To develop an instrument for the identification of SWDs and the evaluation of sleep habits in Mexican children and adolescents, as well as to determine its construct validity and internal consistency within a clinical sample of this population.

■ MATERIALS AND METHODS

Design, Setting, and Period

This was a process study aimed at developing a new instrument and obtaining its validity data. The study was carried out in the outpatient services of the Hospital Psiquiátrico Infantil Dr. Juan N. Navarro (HPIJNN) and the Instituto Nacional de Psiquiatría Ramón de la Fuente Muñiz (INPRFM) in Mexico City, Mexico. Data collection occurred between March 2022 and March 2024.

Sample

A convenience, consecutive sample was drawn,

comprising patients aged six to 17 years from the HPIJNN and INPRFM.

Procedure

The SWDQ was designed and developed by the authors in collaboration with institutional specialists, guided by international classification criteria (AMERICAN PSYCHIATRIC ASSOCIATION [APA], 2000; World Health Organization [WHO], 2004). The SWDQ assesses dyssomnias, parasomnias, and sleep habits using Likert-type frequency statements designed for completion by the parent or guardian. During the instrument's development, attention was given to ensure the items accurately captured the core symptoms of each diagnostic category. The preliminary version of the questionnaire was tested in a pilot study involving 30 participants to evaluate the clarity of items and the overall structure. Based on feedback, items deemed difficult to understand were eliminated, leading to the final version used in this study.

Ethical Aspects

The study adhered to the principles of the Helsinki Declaration. Informed assent and consent were obtained from all participants and their legal guardians. Ethical approval was granted by the Ethics Committees of both institutions: HPIJNN (113/02/1118) and INPRFM (CEI/C/088/2018).

Statistical Analysis

Descriptive statistics were used to analyze demographic variables. Continuous data were summarized using means and standard deviations, while categorical data were expressed as frequencies and percentages.

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Construct validity was evaluated after excluding questions 7, 8, 9, 10, 11, 14, 16, 18, 20, 21, 22, 24, 25, 26, 27, and 29, which addressed enuresis, bruxism, and headbanging due to their limited alignment with direct symptoms of dyssomnias and parasomnias. A principal components exploratory factor analysis (EFA) with Varimax rotation was applied, retaining factors with Eigenvalues greater than one. Internal consistency was determined for each factor using Cronbach's α . All analyses were conducted using SPSS version 29 (International Business Machines Corporation [IBM], 2024).

■ RESULTS**Questionnaire Design**

Through expert consensus, a 43-item SWDQ was developed, comprising two sections: Section A, which included 33 diagnostic questions, and Section B, with 10 questions on sleep habits. Respondents reported high comprehension for most items, with an average completion time of 19 minutes. However, four questions were excluded due to challenges in comprehension, resulting in a final version of the SWDQ consisting of 30 items in Section A and 10 items in Section B.

Sociodemographic and Clinical Characteristics

The study sample included 103 participants, with 66 (61.89%) recruited from the INPRFM and 37 (38.11%) from the HPIJNN. Among the participants, 43 (41.75%) were female, and 60 (58.25%) were male, with a mean age of 13.35 years ($SD = 2.97$). Males were slightly older on average than females (14.3 vs. 12.8 years). Most participants ($n = 86$, 83.5%) attended school regularly, and nearly one-

third ($n = 38$, 36.89%) engaged in sports. A significant proportion ($n = 73$, 70.87%) reported having separated parents.

Regarding clinical diagnoses, internalizing disorders were identified in 19 participants (18.45%), externalizing disorders in 6 (5.83%), neurodevelopmental disorders in 11 (10.68%), and substance/alcohol use disorders in 4 (3.88%). The most frequent diagnosis combinations were mixed internalizing and externalizing disorders ($n = 31$, 30%) and a combination of internalizing, externalizing, and neurodevelopmental disorders ($n = 13$, 12.62%).

Exploratory Factor Analysis

An EFA of 14 items from Section A revealed two principal factors: dyssomnias and parasomnias. Factor loadings and eigenvalues for these components are detailed in **Table 1**.

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Table 1. Exploratory Factor Analysis of the Sleep-Wake Disorders Questionnaire for Children and Adolescents.

Questions	Factor 1 Parasomnias Eigenvalue = 3.657 % of variance= 26.12	Factor 2 Dyssomnias Eigenvalue = 2.06 % of variance= 14.75
1. When your child goes to bed, does he/she have trouble falling asleep?		0.764
2. How long does it take for your child to fall asleep?		0.747
3. Does your child wake up during the night?		0.664
4. Does your child wake up one or two hours earlier than usual?	0.327	
5. Does your child have difficulties staying awake in the mornings?		0.726
6. Does your child fall asleep at school?	0.438	
12. Does your child suddenly wake from sleep scared, sweaty, and unable to fully wake up?	0.738	
13. When your child wakes up from a bad dream, can he/she remember it the next morning?	0.315	
15. Does your child have frightening dreams (nightmares)?	0.550	
17. Does your child sit in bed, stand up, or sleepwalk?	0.641	
19. Does your child complain of leg discomfort or restlessness which improves by moving the legs before falling asleep?	0.653	
23. Does your child complain of leg cramps when falling asleep?	0.545	
28. Does your child talk during their sleep?	0.612	
30. Does it take a lot of effort to wake up in the mornings, or does your child refuse to get up?		0.738

Note: Factor analysis identified two components: Parasomnias and Dyssomnias, explaining 26.12% and 14.75% of the variance, respectively. Factor loadings ≥ 0.30 were considered significant for inclusion in each factor.

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Internal Consistency

Cronbach’s α values indicated moderate internal consistency for parasomnias ($\alpha = 0.68$) but low consistency for dyssomnias ($\alpha = 0.25$).

Sleep Habits

Analysis of Section B revealed notable sleep habits among the participants. Almost one-third of

the sample shared a bedroom with their parents, and fewer than half slept in their own rooms. Napping was prevalent, with 65% of participants reporting regular naps. More than two-thirds adhered to a consistent sleep schedule. Additionally, a high consumption of caffeine-containing beverages was reported. Further details are presented in **Table 2**.

Table 2. Frequencies of the Sleep Habits of the Participants.

Sleep Habits	Frequency (%)
Caffeine intake	69.9
Fluid intake	96.1
Shares bedroom with parents	30.1
Shares bedroom with siblings	20.4
His/her bedroom	44.7
Goes to bed at the same time each night	77.7
Takes naps	
Frequently	23.3
Sometimes	41.7
Never	35
Reads, watches television, exercises, plays, does homework, eats one hour before bedtime	
Frequently	39.8
Sometimes	49.5
Never	9.7

Note: Data from the Sleep-Wake Disorders Questionnaire for Children and Adolescents - Section B: Sleep habits frequency.

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■ DISCUSSION

This study aimed to develop and validate the SWDQ, focusing on its internal consistency, construct validity, and ability to describe sleep habits. The findings support a two-factor structure (dyssomnias and parasomnias) and demonstrate its potential for providing detailed insights into sleep habits.

The sample included a diverse age range and a balanced distribution of sexes among children and adolescents from two different clinical settings. The most frequent diagnoses involved combinations of internalizing and externalizing disorders, as well as internalizing, externalizing, and neurodevelopmental disorders. These findings are consistent with previous research indicating similar prevalence rates of psychiatric comorbidities in pediatric populations with sleep-wake disorders (SWDs) (Cooper et al., 2023; Asarnow & Mirchandaney, 2024; Loram et al., 2023). Emerging diagnostic frameworks such as the Hierarchical Taxonomy of Psychopathology (HiTOP) offer promising approaches to integrate the full spectrum of clinical symptoms with greater precision (Kotov et al., 2022).

Principal components factor analysis revealed two primary factors, which accounted for approximately one-third of the total variance. This suggests that dyssomnias and parasomnias explain a significant portion of the data, while other variables (e.g., physical symptoms like bruxism, breathing difficulties, or leg cramps) may account for the remaining variance. These results align with theoretical models and findings from similar diagnostic tools (Bruni et al., 1996; Chervin et al., 2000), supporting the construct validity of the SWDQ. Internal consistency showed moderate-to-good values for parasomnias but was low

for dyssomnias, potentially reflecting a lower prevalence of dyssomnia-related features in the sample.

The SWDQ also included questions addressing sleep-related behaviors not classified as disorders, offering valuable insights into related behavioral patterns. For instance, the practice of sleeping alone or with parents may impact emotional regulation and independence (Mileva-Seitz et al., 2019), though economic and space constraints are also relevant factors. Notably, 50% of participants reported sleeping with a family member, highlighting the importance of assessing environmental influences on sleep quality.

Additionally, the use of beds for non-sleep activities—such as work, recreation, or consumption of caffeinated beverages—was prevalent. These behaviors are linked to poor sleep hygiene and may contribute to psychopathology (Cooper et al., 2023; Asarnow & Mirchandaney, 2024; Loram et al., 2023). Educating parents on these findings could facilitate improvements in sleep hygiene and habits among children and adolescents.

Regarding future implications, the SWDQ has demonstrated utility in identifying SWDs. Its inclusion of items addressing sleep-related behaviors enhances its comprehensiveness, allowing clinicians to perform a holistic assessment of sleep health in pediatric psychiatric populations.

Limitations

One limitation of the study is the low internal consistency of certain SWDQ factors, which may be due to the wide range of items included to assess various SWDs. A larger sample size is required to refine the factor structure and validate the questionnaire. Future research should also

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evaluate the SWDQ in other pediatric clinical and nonclinical populations, such as those with obesity, respiratory issues, or neurological symptoms.

Strengths

The SWDQ is a comprehensive tool that integrates DSM diagnostic criteria, enhancing its clinical applicability. Its ease of use and clarity, as demonstrated in the pilot test, make it suitable for both clinical and research settings. Future studies should compare the SWDQ with clinical interviews and other standardized diagnostic tools to establish convergent validity. Longitudinal research is needed to assess its predictive validity, test-retest reliability, and utility in monitoring SWDs progression. Additionally, incorporating neurophysiological measures such as actigraphy or polysomnography would provide robust convergent validity.

CONCLUSION

The SWDQ, with its comprehensive scope and integration of diagnostic criteria, is a valid tool for the assessment of SWDs in Mexican pediatric populations. Continued research and refinement will enhance its reliability and clinical utility.

DISCLAIMER

The SWDQ is described in this article for informational purposes only. It is not included as supplemental material. For access to the questionnaire or its use in research or clinical settings, please contact the authors directly to request permission and additional guidelines about its application.

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CONFLICTS OF INTEREST

The authors lack conflicts of interest to disclose.

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